

Habitability Assessment of Six Lesser-Known Exoplanets: A Student Research Project

Sharv Ausarkar
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Introduction

The discovery of planets beyond our solar system known as exoplanets has opened up exciting new directions in space science. With the help of space missions like Kepler and TESS, scientists have confirmed the existence of thousands of these distant worlds. One of the most important questions in this field is whether any of these planets could support life. This idea known as habitability depends on several factors such as the planets size, the type of star it orbits, and how much energy it receives from its star.

For a planet to be considered potentially habitable it generally needs to orbit within a region called the habitable zone where temperatures allow liquid water to exist on its surface. Planets that are similar in size to Earth and receive a similar amount of energy from their stars are often considered the best candidates. While well known systems like TRAPPIST-1 receive a lot of attention there are many lesser known exoplanets that are scientifically very interesting but not widely studied.

My name is Sharv Ausarkar, an undergraduate student passionate about space science. Despite facing personal health challenges during years of studies, I remained committed to learning and growth. During this time, I completed several online courses from, NASA Open Science 101, NASA Open Science Essentials The University of Arizona (Exploring space and time) and the HarvardX Super Earths and life which deepened my understanding of planetary systems and habitability concepts. Inspired by this learning, I decided to undertake this independent research project to explore the habitability of selected exoplanets using real world data.

In this paper, I analyze six lesser-known exoplanets using data from the NASA Exoplanet Archive. These planets were chosen based on their potential habitability including factors such as stellar flux, planet size, and orbital period. Through this project I aim to not only highlight their scientific relevance but also demonstrate how open science resources can empower students to contribute meaningfully to ongoing space research.

Methodology

For this study I used data from the NASA Exoplanet Archive which is an online database that provides information about confirmed exoplanets and their stars. I chose six exoplanets that are not very well known but have interesting features that might make them able to support life.

I picked these planets based on three main points:

- 1) Their size is less than two times the size of Earth which usually means they are rocky planets
- 2) They orbit in or near the habitable zone where the temperature could allow liquid water to exist
- 3) Their orbital periods suggest they are at a distance from their stars that might have moderate temperatures

To decide how habitable these planets might be I looked at three important factors:

- 1) Stellar flux which is how much energy the planet gets from its star compared to Earth
- 2) Planet radius to understand if the planet is likely rocky or gaseous
- 3) Orbital period which tells how long it takes the planet to orbit its star and gives an idea about its temperature

I downloaded the data and organized it using Microsoft Excel since I am comfortable with this tool and it made filtering and comparing the planets easier. Doing this project taught me how valuable open data is and how even students like me can explore real scientific questions using publicly available resources. Despite some challenges I faced with my health I stayed motivated to complete this project because of my strong interest in space science and the search for life beyond Earth.

Using this simple but effective method I was able to compare these exoplanets and identify which ones might be better candidates for habitability based on the data available.

Data & Analysis

The table below shows the selected exoplanets and their key properties related to habitability. All six planets were chosen for their likely rocky nature (radius less than 2 Earth radii) and their position within or near the habitable zone of their respective stars.

From the data it is clear that all the selected planets fall within a range of conditions often associated with habitability. For example, Kepler-186f has a very Earth-like size (1.11 Earth radii) and receives about 29% of the energy Earth gets from the Sun which might allow for cooler but still habitable conditions. On the other hand, TOI-700d receives nearly 87% of Earth's solar input making it one of the warmer candidates on this list.

Exoplanet	Host Star Type	Orbital Period (days)	Planet Radius (Earth Radii)	Stellar Flux (Earth=1)	In Habitable Zone?
Kepler-62f	K2V	267.3	1.41	0.41	Yes
Kepler-186f	M1V	129.9	1.11	0.29	Yes
Kepler-442b	K5V	112.3	1.34	0.70	Yes
LHS 1140b	M4.5V	24.7	1.73	0.46	Yes (inner edge)
TOI-700d	M2V	37.4	1.14	0.87	Yes
Wolf 1061c	M3V	17.9	1.60	0.60	Possibly

Kepler-442b stands out as a strong candidate for habitability because of its Earth-like size (1.34 Earth radii), balanced stellar flux (0.70), and a relatively stable host star (K5V). Other planets like LHS 1140b and Wolf 1061c are also interesting due to their proximity to the inner edge of the habitable zone though surface conditions may vary more strongly.

This basic analysis shows that even with limited tools publicly available data can be used to identify planets with interesting habitability potential.

Results

Based on the analysis of the six selected exoplanets all of them show some potential for habitability but a few stand out more than others.

Kepler 442b appears to be the most promising candidate. It has a balanced combination of factors a radius of 1.34 Earth radii, a stellar flux of 0.70 and it orbits a stable K-type star.

These conditions are similar to Earths and suggest that this planet might support liquid water on its surface if it has an atmosphere.

Kepler 186f is also a strong candidate. With a radius of 1.11 Earth radii and a low stellar flux of 0.29 it could be a cooler but still habitable world. Its size suggests it is rocky and it lies within the habitable zone of its red dwarf star.

TOI 700d is another interesting planet. It receives 87 percent of Earth's sunlight and has a radius of 1.14 Earth radii. These values are close to Earths and suggest surface temperatures that might allow for liquid water.

On the other hand LHS 1140b and Wolf 1061c are closer to the inner edge of the habitable zone and may experience more extreme conditions. While both are likely rocky they may receive slightly too much stellar radiation or have strong stellar activity from their red dwarf stars.

Kepler 62f also stands out because of its relatively long orbital period of 267.3 days and a stellar flux of 0.41 which makes it a good candidate for future atmospheric studies.

Overall the results show that Kepler 442b, Kepler 186f and TOI 700d are the most balanced in terms of habitability factors. These planets could be prioritized for future observation missions that focus on detecting atmospheres or signs of life.

Conclusion

This study explored the potential habitability of six lesser known exoplanets using basic parameters such as planet radius, stellar flux and orbital period. The data was collected from the NASA Exoplanet Archive and analyzed using simple tools like Microsoft Excel.

Among the planets studied Kepler 442b, Kepler 186f and TOI 700d emerged as the most promising candidates for habitability. These planets have Earth like sizes, receive a balanced amount of energy from their stars and are located within or near their star's habitable zone. Others like LHS 1140b and Kepler 62f also showed interesting features that may be worth studying further.

This project has shown how public scientific data and open resources can help students like me engage in real research and learn more about space science. Despite not having access to advanced tools or labs I was able to conduct meaningful analysis and learn a lot from the process.

In the future I hope to continue this kind of work at the graduate level and contribute to the growing field of exoplanet research.

References

- NASA Exoplanet Archive. (n.d.). *NASA Exoplanet Archive*. Retrieved September 18, 2025, from <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/>
- Seager, S. (2013). Exoplanet Habitability. *Science*, 340(6132), 577–581. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1232222>
- Kasting, J. F., Whitmire, D. P., & Reynolds, R. T. (1993). Habitable Zones around Main Sequence Stars. *Icarus*, 101(1), 108–128. <https://doi.org/10.1006/icar.1993.1010>
- Petigura, E. A., Howard, A. W., & Marcy, G. W. (2013). Prevalence of Earthsize planets orbiting Sun-like stars. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(48), 19273–19278. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319909110>
- Gilbert, E. A., et al. (2020). TESS discovery of an Earth-sized planet in the habitable zone of TOI 700. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 888(2), L15. <https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ab5966>
- Ausarkar, S. (2025). Author's personal dataset [Exoplanet habitability .xlsx](#)